

V-disparity based Obstacle Avoidance for Dynamic Path Planning of a Robot-Trailer

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Abstract. Structured space exploration with mobile robots is imperative for autonomous operation in challenging outdoor applications. To this end, robots should be equipped with global path planners that ensure coverage and full exploration of the operational area as well as dynamic local planners that address local obstacle avoidance. The paper at hand proposes a local obstacle detection algorithm based on a fast stereo vision processing step, integrated with a dynamic path planner to avoid the detected obstacles in real-time, while simultaneously keeping track of the global path. It considers a robot-trailer articulated system, based on which the trailer trace should cover the entire operational space in order to perform a dedicated application. This is achieved by exploiting a model predictive controller to keep track of the trailer path while performing stereo vision-based local obstacle detection. A global path is initially posed that ensures full coverage of the operational space and during robot's motion, the detected obstacles are reported in the robot's occupancy grid map, which is considered from a hybrid global and local planner approach to avoid them locally. The developed algorithm has been evaluated in a simulation environment and proved adequate performance.

Keywords: Stereo vision · V-disparity · Path planning · Obstacle avoidance · Model predictive control · Dubins path

1 Introduction

Scene analysis in computer vision frequently requires great computational effort for the modelling and annotation of the existing elements [11]. Normally, one has to make certain assumptions regarding environmental parameters in order to ensure real-time performance. The paper at hand tackles the problems of obstacle extraction and dynamic path planning in order to enable obstacle avoidance for a robot-trailer system that performs autonomous navigation in a flat surface area. Several computer vision based methods have been proposed for scene understanding and obstacle modelling such as the ones described in [3]

and [7], however the closed loop obstacle detection and avoidance in exploration of unknown environments remains an active research topic.

In particular, authors in [9] utilized stereo vision to obtain depth information about the scene followed by feature extraction from V-disparity images to determine whether or not the terrain is traversable by a mobile robot. Another work introduced in [8], a visual odometry algorithm that implements outlier detection and motion estimation based on stereo image pairs resulting in minimal positioning errors has been presented. In [11], an obstacle detection method using dynamic pitching of the vehicle to deal with non-flat terrains has been exhibited. The approach relied on V-disparity images to gain geometric information about the road scene and performed semi-global matching without explicitly extracting coherent structures in the stereo image pair. A combination of a stereo camera with a monocular has been used to perform obstacle detection and state estimation respectively, for outdoor flights of micro air vehicles. [13]. The method allows for scalability and generalizations regarding obstacle representation and additional sensor fusion. Work in [19] tackles obstacle extraction and 3D position estimation using disparity and V-disparity images for the purposes of driving support. Y. Gao et al. [5] employ an uncalibrated 3D camera to generate a depth map used to calculate U-disparity and V-disparity images that contain line representations of obstacles and ground surface. Line extraction is realized with an optimized Hough transform [4] after the addition of steerable filters for noise reduction. In [1], an artificial intelligence (AI) vision method for obstacle detection in real-time in unstructured environments is proposed. Again, the V-disparity image is exploited to estimate the camera pitch oscillation caused by the vehicle's motion while stereo matching is used for the extraction and mapping of the obstacles in 3D coordinates. Authors in [16], demonstrated an obstacle detection algorithm based on U-disparity. The method examined the uncertainty of stereo vision by incorporating a probabilistic representation taking into account distance and disparity values. R. Mandelbaum et al. [12], used a next-generation video processor to develop real-time stereo processing as well as obstacle/terrain detection from stereo cameras installed on a moving vehicle. Stereo vision has been used for road and free space detection by separating them through color segmentation [18]. The proposed approach utilized an extended V-disparity algorithm that also incorporated U-disparity to successfully classify varying road profiles. The work presented in [22] discussed a global correlation method for ground plane extraction from V-disparity images in featureless roads. The method applied for on and off-road navigation by vehicles with vision-based obstacle detection. Authors in [6] presented a road scene analysis algorithm based on stereo vision as a supplement to radar-based analysis. U-V-disparity have been used for 3D road scene classification into surface planes characterizing the road's features. Sappa et al. [17] introduced two road plane approximation techniques, the first utilizing U-disparity and Hough transform and the second using least squares fitting to find the optimal fitting plane for the whole point cloud data. The benefits of stereo vision compared to other sensing technologies have been emphasized in [14], which proposed another usage of U-V-disparity

for the purpose of modelling an urban environment. V-disparity has been also used by an unmanned ground vehicle (UGV) to perform obstacle detection, in order to obtain terrain information and enable navigation in more complex surfaces [21]. Authors in [15] proposed a new method for 3D scene representation named theta-disparity which has been calculated from a disparity image as a 2D angular depth histogram and revealed radial distribution of existing objects relative to a point of interest.

In this work, obstacle extraction based on V-disparity images incorporated into a hybrid local/global path planning algorithm has been developed, with the purpose of being integrated in a real robot-trailer system. Regarding the models used in simulation, the mobile robot is a SUMMIT XL robot produced by Robotnik and a two-wheeled trailer that carries Ground Penetrating Radar produced by IDS GeoRadar. The GPR is not exploited in this work, however the embodiment of the GPR antenna is considered in the robot’s path planning and re-planning, to address the demand in similar application scenarios, where the sensor/device mounted on the robot’s trailer is utilized for a dedicated purpose, such as plowing in agricultural robotic applications. The ZED stereo camera is mounted in front of the robot-trailer’s tow hitch. The goal of this paper is twofold; firstly, the presentation of a method that assures obstacle avoidance from both the robot vehicle and the trailer part, assuming a flat ground plane in the vicinity of the vehicles, where obstacle extraction is employed and, secondly, the method guarantees that the GPR-equipped trailer keeps on following the updated path after local obstacle avoidance.

2 Processing of stereo image pairs

2.1 Disparity and V-disparity computation

Fig. 1. a) Left camera image, b) right camera image, c) resulting disparity image

The ZED camera has been mounted on the robot’s body with a pitch angle of around 17° , since most of visual input should be the ground surface along with existing obstacles, to maximize input for robot navigation. Disparity images have been calculated using a standard local block matching stereo vision algorithm as 8-bit grayscale images using the pair of left and right images captured from the

stereo camera. The left rectified stereo image has been considered as reference for the disparity image calculations. D_{min} and D_{max} are the parameters that quantify the expected minimum and maximum disparity, and in our case they are set equal to 0 and 111 respectively, assuming planar robot operation. A pair of grayscale stereo images captured from the camera as well as the calculated disparity image are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 2. a) Disparity image, b) respective V-disparity image, c) reference image with highlighted obstacles

After obtaining depth information from the disparity image, the V-disparity image is calculated to extract knowledge about obstacles and the plane of the ground surface. Each row of the V-disparity image is calculated as a histogram of the varying disparities in the corresponding row of the disparity image. The number of columns is equal to the discrete disparity values. Thus, given a disparity image of size (W, H) and the parameters D_{min} and D_{max} , the resulting V-disparity image will have a size equal to $(D_{max} - D_{min} + 1, H)$. As an example, we may consider a disparity image of size $(10, H)$, $D_{min} = 0$ and $D_{max} = 5$ with the first row being equal to $[2, 0, 4, 4, 1, 0, 2, 4, 5, 2]$. After applying the binning principle, the resulting first row in the V-disparity image will be equal to $[2, 1, 3, 0, 3, 1]$. After finishing the calculations, the pixel values are mapped to $[0, 255]$ range for visualization purposes. A pair of disparity and V-disparity images along with the reference image with highlighted obstacles are depicted in Fig. 2.

2.2 Obstacle extraction from V-disparity

Using the sparse disparity map obtained from the stereo correspondence algorithm, a reliable V-disparity image is computed where each pixel has a positive integer value that denotes the number of pixels in the input image that lie on the same image line (ordinate) and have disparity value equal to its abscissa [10]. The information resulting from the V-disparity image is of great importance because it easily distinguishes the pixels belonging to the ground plane from the ones belonging to obstacles. The ground plane in the V-disparity image can be modeled by a linear equation, the parameters of which can be found

using Hough transform, if the geometry of the camera-environment system is unknown. However, if the geometry of the system is constant and known, as in a case of a camera firmly mounted on a robot exploring a planar outdoors environment, then the two parameters can be easily computed beforehand and used in all the image pairs during the exploration. Looking top-down in Fig. 2(a), the increasing pixel intensity expresses the decreasing distance between the camera and the ground plane. Thus, it holds true that pixels corresponding to obstacles present in the camera’s field of view (FoV), have a positive intensity and appear above the characteristic line in a V-disparity image. This effect is demonstrated in Fig. 2(b) which illustrates an obstacle that has been placed away from the camera.

Yet, the hypothesis of a perfectly flat floor never stands in practice, either because of the floor actually not being perfectly flat or because of small disparity estimation and discretization errors. As a result, a tolerance region extending on both sides of the linear segment of the terrain has to be defined and any point outside of it can then be safely considered as originating from an obstacle. For each row in the V-disparity image, pixels that satisfy the aforementioned criterion have their column numbers (disparity values) stored in a set. Then, pixels with disparities contained in the corresponding sets are traced back in the disparity image and marked as obstacles in the original reference image, as depicted in Fig. 2(c).

After tracking the pixels (x_p, y_p) that correspond to obstacles in the original left camera image of size (W, H) , 3D reconstruction of the pixels that correspond to obstacles in world frame are realized taking into consideration the stereo camera model. Thus, if f is the camera’s focal length measured in pixels and b is the camera’s baseline, transformed (x, y, z) coordinates with respect to the camera’s frame are given by:

$$(x, y, z) = \left(\frac{z \cdot (x_p - x_c)}{f}, \frac{z \cdot (y_p - y_c)}{f}, \frac{f \cdot b}{disp(x_p, y_p)} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $(x_c, y_c) = (\frac{W}{2}, \frac{H}{2})$ is the image’s central pixel and $disp(x_p, y_p)$ is the disparity value of pixel (x_p, y_p) .

Fig. 3(a) depicts the robot in a stationary position observing an obstacle in the simulation environment and Fig. 3(b) depicts the 3D reconstructed obstacles extracted from the V-disparity process as point cloud in front of the robot. It is apparent that the method manages to extract every obstacle in the camera’s FoV without being limited to the robot’s vicinity. However in our case obstacles that are greater than a predefined threshold add extra computational cost thus, in order to achieve real-time performance, the camera’s maximum depth range is limited to 2.5 m, an adequate distance for the robot to detect and avoid an obstacle in time.

Fig. 3. a) Simulation environment and b) extracted obstacles from V-disparity as a 3D point cloud

3 Dynamic path planning and obstacle avoidance

To achieve robot-trailer coverage of the entire surface multiple passes are required. The global path to be followed by the robot-trailer is constructed as a Dubins path that utilizes the boustrophedon motion algorithm [2] although differing from a standard boustrophedon path since it involves unidirectional instead of bidirectional turns (see Fig. 4(b)). During the robot-trailer exploration, existence of obstacles is unknown to the global planner. Thus, obstacles detected by the robot during navigation are reported to the occupancy grid map as occupied cells in order to be avoided (see Fig. 4(c)).

For the obstacle modeling inside the robot navigation environment, point clouds of extracted obstacles (see Fig. 4(d)) are projected to the occupancy grid map (OGM) that expresses occupancy states in the ground plane. The value of each cell of OGM represents the probability of the cell to be occupied. Cell's state is mainly interpreted as free, occupied or unknown according to how the user handles the cell values. The OGM, used as a costmap herein, is initialized around the robot's initial position. As the robot-trailer explores the previously unknown environment, it constantly expands the visible costmap in accordance to the obtained obstacles from the V-disparity procedure, to cover previously unknown area that is currently inside the camera's FoV and under the 2.5 m threshold.

By taking into consideration occupied cells that intersect with planned way-points by the Dubins path planner, a custom made parametric local obstacle avoidance has been developed. The latter considers the intersected way-points of the global planner with the obstacles and infers an arc trajectory that bypasses the reported obstacles. The inferred arc obeys to the robot-trailer kinematic constraints and does not exceed the maximum hitch angle between the robot and the trailer (see Fig. 4(d)). The length of the arc is proportional to the distance required for the trailer to avoid the obstacle. Thus each time an obstacle is presented at the robot's retina, i.e. V-disparity obstacle detection system, the robot re-plans a trajectory around the obstacle that forces the robot-trailer

module to avoid the obstacle and keep the co-linear trajectory to the Dubins path. This method allows maximum coverage to the explored environment and deviation from the global plan only for the avoidance of small previously unseen obstacles. In situations where the robot-trailer cannot meet again the Dubins path i.e. the trailer exhibits a predefined threshold of 0.5 m, a re-plan of the Dubins path is requested from the global planner.

In order to ensure accurate robot-trailer exploration that obeys to the drawn paths, robot pose estimation and path tracking modules have also been incorporated into the system. Robot pose estimation is performed through stereo-based visual odometry, which is mostly relied in 3D features tracking [8], exploiting the disparity map computed for the obstacle detection. For the local navigation and in order to closely follow the Dubins path, a model predictive controller (MPC) has been implemented as an optimal approach to solve the path tracking problem for the robot-trailer system [20]. MPC is a control method used to control a process while satisfying a set of constraints and in our approach, a linear model has been implemented in order to enhance real-time performance. The goal of MPC, quite common in robot-trailer systems, is the elimination of the trailer's lateral position error.

Fig. 4. a) Gazebo environment containing obstacle, b) Boustrophedon path, c) Re-planned path with curved segment, d) Re-planned path with obstacle's 3D point cloud reconstruction

4 Experimental evaluation

The performance of the implemented methods has been evaluated in a simulation environment. Fig. 4(a) depicts the environment with the robot-trailer in its stationary initial position. The Dubins path to be followed by the trailer, is illustrated in green color in Fig. 4(b). Fig. 4(c) shows a top view of the scene after obstacle extraction through V-disparity and re-planning application of the re-planning procedure. Specifically, the cone's area marked on the costmap along with the added path segment that bypasses the obstacle are exhibited in the same figure whereas the cone's point cloud reconstruction is better perceived in 4(d). In a more large-scale experiment, the robot-trailer bypasses several obstacles during the traversal of the Dubins path as illustrated in Fig. 5. The paths followed by the robot and trailer are depicted in red and blue color respectively along with the Dubins path. It is revealed that the proposed dynamic obstacle avoidance and planning algorithm manages to bypass the obstacles and at the same time closely follows the imposed path with absolute deviation error in the trajectory less than 0.5 m, measured through the ground-truth observations of the Gazebo simulation environment.

Fig. 5. a) Initialization with Dubins path, b) detected and reported obstacle in the cost map, c) local replan on the Dubins path and (d)-(h) continuous path tracking and replanning. Replanned reference Dubins path (green color) with actual robot path (red color) and actual trailer path (blue color)

5 Conclusions

In this work, a method for maximum coverage of a surface area with an articulated robot-trailer setup has been presented. During the exploration, obstacle

detection has been performed based on stereo vision, which is then exploited by a dynamic path planner in a closed loop obstacle avoidance scheme. V-disparity has been utilized for the detection of obstacles above the surface plane which are isolated as pixels in the stereo reference image and 3D reconstructed to be expressed as occupied cells in the robot's occupancy grid map. Robot exploration is performed through structured Dubins path planning which is dynamically updated with smaller local paths that allow real-time obstacle avoidance and enable co-linearity with the initial global path after the avoidance routine. The method has been integrated with stereo-based visual motion estimation and MPC, that allows constant path tracking during robot-trailer exploration. The method assures that the robot-trailer is able to avoid small obstacles while the trailer is kept in the added segment and whenever possible, keeps on following the initial path after avoiding the obstacle.

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